

SEVEN NAMUYI TIBETAN SIBLINGS: WECHAT GROUP CONVERSATION

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ABSTRACT

WeChat provides a forum for seven Namuyi Tibetans to discuss and often resolve issues quickly in their mother tongue. This paper describes a discussion that took place on 19 April 2019 between 21:08-22:00 hours. The siblings discussed where Jibu's daughter, Guifeng (b. 2007), should attend junior middle school. The seven siblings' educational background is described, and their conversations in na⁵³ mzi⁵³ kha¹¹ tho¹¹ (Namuyi Khatho) are given and transcribed, along with a free English translation.

KEYWORDS

family education discussions, Namuyi Tibetans, WeChat, Tibetan minority languages, Namuyi Khatho, Sichuan minorities

INTRODUCTION

The eastern border of the Tibetan Plateau is home to 5,000-10,000 Namuyi (na⁵³ mzi⁵³) Tibetans (Sun 1983, Gutao and Wang 2012) who speak Namuyi Khatho (na⁵⁴ mzi⁵⁴ kha²¹ tho²¹), which is classified as Qiangic (Sun 1983, Jacquest and Michaud 2011) in Muli Tibetan Autonomous County, Xichang City, Mianning County, and Jiulong County of Sichuan Province, PR China.¹

A WeChat group with seven members (myself and my six siblings) was created and named "Seven Siblings":

FIG 1. Seven siblings.

Name	Sex	Birth Date	Education
Li Xiaolong	M	1965	PS ²
Li Bajin	M	1974	PS
Li Chunxiu	F	1977	PS
Li Jiujin	M	1979	PS
Li Jianfu	M	1981	university
Li Jibu	M	1984	PS
Li Sanjin	F	1986	PS

Only Li Jianfu of the siblings has a good command of written Chinese. While all siblings received some primary school education, most did not graduate. Only Chinese and mathematics were taught in the village primary school at the time the siblings attended. Xiaolong attended middle school for one year but dropped out due to a lack of interest. He occasionally uses written Chinese because he is the Dashui Village leader and must fill out forms and write villagers' names in Chinese. Bajin and Chunxiu did not have a chance to go to primary school because our parents wanted them to work at home. Later, when Bajin was eighteen and Chunxiu was fifteen, our parents realized the importance

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¹ For more on the Namuyi, see Libu Lakhi et al. (2007, 2009, 2013).

² PS = primary school.

of knowing basic mathematics and written Chinese and sent them to Dashui Village Primary School. However, they both decided to drop out after Grade Two because they were embarrassed when their classmates and teachers laughed at them for being "old."

Jiujin had a strong interest in learning and made good scores on exams until the fifth grade when his mathematics teacher scolded him for being naughty in class. "Afterward, I totally lost interest in learning, and I slept in class," Jiujin says.

Jianfu, Jibu, and Sanjin both finished primary school.

WeChat group members use (oral) Namuyi, though Jianfu, Jibu, and Sanjin converse at times in written Chinese. They discuss issues involving the siblings, including updating each other on their current location and activities. At times, input is sought on topics such as what action to take or which hospital to visit during an illness and matters related to children's education.

The example I present here concerns Jibu's daughter, Li Guifeng (b. 2007), who would graduate from primary school in June 2019. On the night of 19 April 2019, Jibu started a conversation by forwarding a screenshot of a text message sent by a teacher from Chuanzhong Middle School responsible for recruiting students who make high scores from primary schools. At this time, Xiaolong and Bajin were at their own homes having dinner in Dashui Village, Chunxiu was in Pixian County near Chengdu working in a meat processing factory, Jiujin was completing a gate for a new house his family had started building, I was in Chengdu, Jibu was at home in Xingsheng Town, and Sanjin was at her home taking care of her daughter in Yulong Town.

The conversations below focus on the junior middle school that Guifeng should attend. Two points should be made regarding the talks. First, the IPA (International Phonetic Alphabet) transcriptions are directly transcribed from the Namuyi voice message records kept in the WeChat group conversation loop. The few times Chinese characters are used, they are not transcribed in IPA. Second, conversations are arranged chronologically. Certain entries are short utterances, and others are more than one sentence. Each pair of IPA transcriptions and their English translation represents a complete voice message.

Voice messages are from 9:08-10:00PM.

[1] Jibu: (Jibu's screenshot of a written message sent by Teacher Yang from Chuanzhong Middle School.)

李贵芬家长你好！麻烦你们帮川中问一下边这几个学生的电话，问到后请用短信发给我：陈紫婧、李贵芬、孙文泉、杨佳茹、李雨晨、郑丽佳、吴思颖、肖佳英。

Hi, Li Guifeng's parents! May I ask you to assist Chuanzhong Middle School by providing the phone numbers of the following students? Chen Zijin, Li Guifeng, Sun Wenquan, Yang Jiaru, Li Yuchen, Zhen Lijia, Wu Siyi, Xiao Jiaying. Please send them to me.

[2] Xiaolong:

啥意思

What does this mean?

[3] Jibu:

o²¹mo²¹ t^hwæ⁵⁴t^ʂo⁵⁴ t^hwæ⁵⁴t^ʂo⁵⁴ ɛwo²¹ɛo²¹ t^ʂo⁵⁴ si⁵⁴ pæ²¹ ɲo⁵⁴ kwe²¹fa³³ t^ʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ ji²¹ lo²¹.
Oh, it's about Chuanzhong Middle School coming to recruit my daughter, Guifeng.

[4] Xiaolong:

kwe²¹fa³³ t^ʂo⁵⁴ su⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ o³³da³⁴ po²¹mi²¹ da³³ ɲu²¹ su²¹ djɛ³⁴?

Does that mean they are asking Guifeng to register in that school?

[5] Jibu:

a²¹ n̩²¹ o³³da³⁴ tʂ^hə²¹te^ə²¹ k^hi³⁴ t^hi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ t^hi²¹te^hæ²¹-mu⁵⁴ ɛwo²¹ɛo²¹ tʂo⁵⁴ da²¹ ku⁵¹ so³³; t^hi³³-hi²¹ o³³da³⁴ tʂ^hæ⁵⁴tʂo³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²³ lo³³; væ³³qæ³⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³⁴ ma⁵⁴ sə⁵⁴ n̩³³-ly³⁴ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ ro³³ ji²¹ lo²¹.

Em, for the students with high scores, schools usually come and recruit them in advance, right? Chuanzhong Middle School wants to recruit her, and I heard that two other schools - I don't know their exact names - also came to her school recruiting students.

[6] Xiaolong:

go⁵⁴-ly³⁴ k^hi³³ tɛ⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³⁴ mi²¹ po²¹ ma³³-ya³⁴ ji²¹ a²¹?

Can't we just send her to whichever school is best?

[7] Jiujin:

哦

OK.

[8] Bajin:

o³⁴, tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ mi²¹ la²¹tɛ²¹ mje³³. ŋa³³ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂu⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ lo²¹tɛ²¹ ræ³⁴ tɛ^ha²¹ ma³³ p^ha⁵⁴ lɛ²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ ŋa⁵⁴-hi²¹ so³³-ja²¹-su⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴. tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂu⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ to²¹ma²¹ndza²¹-su⁵⁴ dja³³ lɛ²¹. tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴-mi²¹ tɛ^ha²¹ mje³³ tɛ⁵⁴ la³⁴-mi⁵⁴-po²¹ ŋu²¹ mje²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ ræ⁵⁴ a²¹ tʂo⁵⁴ mu³³.

OK, if Chuanzhong Middle School has come to recruit her, then let her register there. My three children could not even go to Liangshan Prefecture Nationalities Middle School. Chuanzhong Middle School is considered better than Liangshan Prefecture Nationalities Middle School. Let her register there and see if she is recruited.

[9] Jibu:

还不晓得去哪里读

I still don't know where I should send her.

[10] Jibu:

go⁵⁴ ræ⁵⁴ a²¹-tʂo⁵⁴ ŋu²¹ ti²¹-ga²¹ dzo³³ ku²³ lɛ³³? su⁵⁴ ji⁵⁴te^o³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹-ro³³ lo³³. tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ na³³ væ³³qæ³⁴ ti²¹-ly³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ n̩³³-ly³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹-ro³³ lo³³. tɛ³³ væ³³qæ⁵⁴ t^hi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴. væ³³qæ⁵⁴ t^hi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴ ɛo²¹ɛo²¹ go⁵⁴-ly³³ p^hæ³³ k^hi³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴ ŋu²¹-su²¹ lo²¹. nu³³ o⁵⁴ so²¹ bjɛ²¹ tɛ^hy⁵⁴ ka³³ su⁵⁴ ji⁵⁴te³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹-su⁵⁴-ro³³ lɛ²¹.

What do you mean by "if she is recruited?" They already have come to recruit. Chuanzhong and another school - two schools - have already come to recruit her. But I know nothing about the other one. I mean, I don't know anything about the other one, so I don't know which one is better. Otherwise, people have already come there to recruit her if she is willing to study there.

[11] Bajin:

tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ p^hæ³³ ti²¹ ji²¹ mi²¹ dja³³ lɛ²². tʂ^hwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ p^hæ³³ k^hi³³ dja³³ lɛ²². o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ la²¹ k^ho³³ʂə²¹ ku³⁴ sə³³ ŋu²¹ nu⁵⁴ lɛ³⁴. k^ho³³ʂə²³ ka³³ ma³³ ta²¹to²¹-su⁵⁴ ma³³-n̩⁵⁴ ku²³ sə³³. n̩²¹mu²¹n̩³³ ŋa⁵¹ kwe⁵¹fa²¹ la²¹ te²¹ja²¹ tewi⁵⁴ɛo²¹ tʂo⁵⁴ ɛy³⁴ a³³ o³³ k^ho⁵⁴ lɛ⁵⁴ ma³³-ræ³³ da³⁴ kwe²¹fa³³ tɛ⁵⁴ k^hi³⁴ ka³³ tʂ^he²¹te^ə²¹ k^hi³⁴-ro³³ ka³³ t^hi³³-hi²¹ o³³da³³ to³³ lɛ³³ la²¹ bjɛ³⁴-su³³ ma³³-di³³ tɛ³³.

Chuanzhong is best. Chuanzhong is better. Even when they come to recruit, students are usually still given exams. And they don't take those who don't pass the exams. Before my son, Guifa, was recruited by Deyang Military School and didn't pass the exam, or maybe Guifeng's scores are already good enough to reach the required level, so she won't be given more exams.

[12] Jibu:

a²¹mi³³ ta²¹mu³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ tʰi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ kʰo³³ʂə²¹ ma³³-hu⁵⁴-mu⁵⁴ pi²¹ni²³ ka³³ o⁵⁴ po²¹mi²¹ bjɛ²³-su⁵⁴ kʰo³³ʂə²¹ ma³³-hu⁵⁴-su⁵⁴.

Now, students recruited like this just go directly for registration; no need to take more exams.

[13] Sanjin:

先问问别人，和另外一个学校对比。

First, ask for advice from others; and compare it with the other school.

[14] Jibu:

ɛi²¹ tɛo²¹ʂə³⁴ ŋa⁵⁴ ɦa³³ tʰi⁵⁴ ŋu²¹-su²¹ dja³³. vɛ³³qæ⁵⁴ ɛo²¹ɛo²¹-tʰi³³-ly³⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³⁴ dja³³-su⁵⁴ sə²¹ sə³³ŋi³⁴ twe²¹pi⁵⁴ lɛ⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³³ kʰi³³-su⁵⁴ mi²¹do³³ lɛ³³ go⁵⁴-ly³³ so²³ ŋu²²-su²¹ lo²¹.

Yes, I'm also thinking that way. Let her study in the better one after figuring out the other school and comparing them.

[15] Bajin:

kwe²¹fa⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-ɦi²¹ pæ⁵⁴ ɣo⁵⁴ tɛə⁵²mi²¹ tʂæ²³ ji²¹ lɛ²¹ a²¹mi³³? tʂʰwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ ɦa³³ kʰi³³ nda³⁴ ro²¹ lo³³ ŋa³³ ly²¹ tɛ⁵⁴.

What's Guifeng's score ranking in her class now? I think Chuanzhong is already very good.

[16] Jibu:

tʰi⁵⁴-ɦi²¹ pæ⁵⁴ ɣo⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ ti²¹ ji²¹ mi²¹ tʂæ²¹ so³³ ti²¹ ji²¹ mi²¹ tʂæ²¹. ɛiŋ⁵⁴ʂe²¹ ɛa⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ ɤo⁵⁴ mu⁵⁴ta⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ ti²¹-ga²¹ tɛ²¹ ti²¹ ə:²¹ mi²¹ tʂæ²¹ ti²¹-ga²¹ tɛ²¹ ti²¹ sæ²¹ mi²¹ tʂæ²¹-su⁵⁴ lo⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-tɛo²¹ tɛʰə⁵⁴mo²¹ kʰo⁵⁴ʂə²¹-su⁵⁴ ʂaŋ²³ ɛo²¹tɛʰə³³. tʰi⁵⁴-ɦi²¹ tʰi⁵⁴ ji²¹ pæ⁵⁴ ɣo⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ ji²¹tʂə²¹-mu⁵⁴ ti²¹ ji²¹ mi²¹ tɛʰa²³ tɛə²¹ tɛə²¹-su²¹ dja³³ lɛ²¹. jo²¹pu²¹jo²¹ ti²¹-rə²¹ rə²³ da²¹ ti²¹ ə:²¹ mi²¹ tɛʰa²¹ rə³³.

According to the total scores of last semester's exams, she is first in her class. And Chinese is second, and mathematics is third among all the Xingsheng Town students. She is first in her class most of the time, except a few times, she is second.

[17] Xiaolong:

tʂʰwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ kʰi³³ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂʰwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ mi²¹ tɛʰa ʂə⁵⁴-ro³³. ŋa⁵⁴ lɛ³³ ti²¹-ga²¹ ɦa³³ ma³³-sə⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³³ kʰi³³ ɦa³³ ŋa³³ ma³³-sə⁵⁴ xo³³. ta²¹mu³³ ɦa³³ mi²¹do³³ ɦa³³ ma³³-ndzo²¹.

If Chuanzhong is better, let her go there. For me, I don't know anything about which one is better. I also have never asked anything about such an issue.

[18] Chunxiu:

kʰi³³ nda⁵⁴ lɛ²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ kwe²¹fa⁵⁴ pʰæ³³ su⁵⁴ ɦa³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ su⁵⁴ tɛ³³. go⁵⁴-ly³³ kʰi³³-su⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ly³³ tɛʰa²¹ mjɛ⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴. ŋo⁵⁴ ɦa³³ ti²¹-ga²¹ ɦa³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴ lɛ²¹.

Guifa is excellent, so schools even come to recruit her in advance. Let her go to the one that you all think is good. I also don't know anything about this matter.

[19] Bajin:

kʰi³⁴ xo²¹ tɛ³³ su⁵⁴ tɛʰa²¹ nda³³ xo²¹ tɛ³³ ɛa⁵⁴-ly³³ qo²¹lo³³ ɣo⁵⁴ ti²¹ ə:²¹ sæ³³ mi²¹ tɛʰa²¹ su³³. tʰi⁵⁴ la²¹da³³ nɿi⁵⁴-ku²¹ da²¹ jo²³-su⁵⁴ dja³³ lɛ³³ ɛa⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ qo²¹lo³³ ɣo⁵⁴ ɦa³³.

Great, really great, that she makes second or third even within one township. There are only two students who make higher scores among all the township students.

[20] Jibu:

ɛi²¹, do⁵⁴bzə²¹-su⁵⁴ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ bjɛ³⁴ sə³³ ɣa³³-ro²¹ pa³³ o³³. tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ qʰa²¹gu²¹ ɕa²¹ ɦa³³ kʰi³³ ji²¹ rə²¹.

Yes, I probably should let her go to Chuanzhong. Everyone says Chuanzhong is good.

[21] Bajin:

tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ tɕoŋ²¹tjɛ⁵⁴pæ⁵⁴ lo²¹ ræ³³ ɕa²³ ka³³ o³³ a⁵⁴ko⁵⁴ nda³³ kʰi³³ nda³³-su⁵⁴ dja³³.

It's already really great once she enters a *zhongdian ban*¹ class of Chuanzhong.

[22] Sanjin:

tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴-ly⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ o⁵⁴ndzɔ⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-rə⁵⁴ka⁵⁴ go⁵⁴-ti²¹-ku²¹ du³³ ku²¹ ɛɛ²¹? ɲa³³ tɛ⁵⁴ faŋ⁵⁴ɛa²¹ ɲa³³ li³³ŋo²¹pæ³³-ro²¹ lo³³

In which direction or place from Xichang is Chuanzhong located? I forget the direction of that school.

[23] Bajin:

o²¹tjo²¹ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴ɛiŋ⁵⁴ rə⁵⁴ka⁵⁴ dja³³ ka³³ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ ɲu²¹-su²¹ dja³³ lɛ²¹ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴ɛiŋ⁵⁴ jo²¹jo³³-su⁵⁴ dja³³ ka³³.

It is in the direction of Chuanxing with Chuanxing Town, so it is called Chuangzhong.

[24] Jiujin:

a³³bo⁵⁴ tɛ³³ fa⁵⁴fa⁵⁴ pʰæ³³ a⁵⁴ko⁵⁴-ro²¹ ɛiŋ⁵⁴ɕe²¹ ɛa⁵⁴ ɣo⁵⁴ ɦa³³ ti²¹ ə:²¹ mi²¹ ti²¹ sæ³³ mi²¹ ræ³³-tɕæ²¹-su³³. ɛo²¹ɛo²¹ tɛ²¹ ta²¹ko³³ ma⁵⁴-ɕa⁵⁴-mu⁵⁴ ɲa⁵⁴ ɦa³³ go⁵⁴-ly³³ kʰi³³-ma³³-kʰi³³-su⁵⁴ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴. tɕo⁵⁴mi²¹tɕoŋ³³ mi²¹dzu²¹ ku²¹ rə³³ ɣu⁵⁴ta²¹ tɛ³³ ɲa³³ tɛ⁵⁴ tɕo⁵⁴mi²¹tɕoŋ³³ sə³³ a⁵⁴ko⁵⁴-su⁵⁴ tɕa³³ mjɛ³³

Wow! Guifeng is really amazing to score second or third among all Xingsheng Township students. Concerning the schools, as our eldest brother has said, I also don't know which school is good and which school is bad. It seems that the Prefecture Nationalities Middle School is famous and I think it is really great.

[25] Jiujin:

a³³vu³⁴ pʰe²¹ni²¹xwa²¹ tɛ²¹ la²¹ tɕo⁵⁴mi²¹tɕoŋ³³ li³³ ɣæ⁵⁴ɕə⁵⁴ ja²¹ŋə³³ tɛ⁵⁴ la²¹ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ li³³ ɣæ⁵⁴ɕə⁵⁴ mu⁵⁴ o³³mbæ⁵⁴ so³³ ha³³ ji³³ɕo⁵⁴ ti²¹kʰa³³. a²¹mi³³ su⁵⁴ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ o³³ tɕo⁵⁴ dzy²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ o³³ tɕʰwæ⁵⁴tɕo⁵⁴ tɛʰa²¹ ɣo³³ da²¹rə³³-ro²¹ jɛ³³.

A while ago, Awu Penihua² was aiming at the Prefecture Nationalities Middle School, and Jibu was aiming at Chuanzhong. I think if Chuanzhong has come to recruit her, it is reasonable for her to go to Chuanzhong now.

¹ A *zhongdian ban* class consists of gifted students who make high scores on middle school entrance exams. Some schools directly collect such students in their last year of primary school without taking exams.

² Awu Penihua is Jibu's wife's father.

[25] Bajin:

tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂoŋ³³ tʂhwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ ji²¹kʰu³³ dja³³ sə³³ ŋu²¹

The Prefecture Nationalities Middle School is not as good as Chuanzhong.

[26] Jibu:

tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂoŋ³³ tɛ⁵⁴ pu²¹tsu²¹ n̩i³³ka³³ dzo³³ ku²³ ji²¹ lɛ³³ pu²¹tsu²¹ o²¹mo²¹ tʂhwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ bi²¹ji³³ ma³³-dzo²¹ ji²¹ lo²¹ teao²¹ɛwe²¹ tʂə²¹nja²¹ tɛ²¹.

People say there are subsidy opportunities in the Prefecture Nationalities Middle School, but the teaching quality is not as good as Chuanzhong.

[27] Xiaolong:

o²¹mo²¹ su⁵⁴ o³³ so²¹ ndzo²¹ tʰi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴ da⁵⁴ mi²¹do³³ mjɛ⁵⁴. ŋo⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ ta²¹su⁵¹ fia³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴. ŋo⁵⁴ ko²¹mi⁵⁴ fia³³ n̩i²¹mu²¹n̩i³³ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂoŋ⁵⁴ so²¹ rə²¹. tʰɛ⁵⁴ ndzə²¹ tʰi³³ lo²¹-mu²¹ po²¹mi²¹ tʰɛ⁵⁴ ndzə²¹ tʰi³³ lo²¹-so²¹ ka³³ go⁵⁴-ly³³ kʰi²³ fia³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴ ŋa³³ tɛ³³.

Ask those who studied there. I don't know about these things at all. My daughter, Guomin, studied at Xichang Nationalities Middle School. She registered for that school and studied there independently, but I don't know very much.

[28] Jibu:

o²¹ do⁵⁴bzə²¹-su⁵⁴ tʂhwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ so²¹ bjɛ²¹ da²¹rə³³ pa³³ o³³. tɛ³³ su⁵⁴ ʂa²¹-su²¹ ma³³-ti²¹ga²¹ sə²¹ lo³³. ti²¹ki²¹ tɛ²¹ jan²¹kwa³³ kʰi³³-ro²¹ sə³³ ji²¹ o²¹. ti²¹ki²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ ji²¹tʂoŋ⁵⁴ kʰi³³-ro²¹ sə³³ ji²¹ o²¹. ti²¹ki²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂoŋ³³ kʰi³³-ro²¹ sə³³ ji²¹ o²¹ mu³³ ka³³ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴-ro²¹ sə³³.

She should possibly go to Chuanzhong, but people say different things. Some say Yangguang Middle School is good. Some say Number One Middle School is good. Some say the Prefecture Nationalities Middle School is good. I'm just not sure.

[29] Jiujiu:

qʰa⁵⁴ kʰi³³ qʰa⁵⁴ kʰi³³ fia³³ go³³zə⁵⁴ ti²¹pʰæ³³ ɛo²¹ɛo²¹ kʰi³³ ʂə⁵⁴ʂə⁵⁴-ly³³ ræ⁵⁴-so⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ go³³zə⁵⁴ tʂhe²¹teə²¹ a⁵⁴ko⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ o³³ kʰi³³-su³³ rə⁵⁴ lɛ²¹.

It doesn't matter which school is good or bad. It's good as long as the child can get into a medium-quality school with a medium score.

[30] Jianfu:

ŋa³³ tɛ⁵⁴ nu³³ mbæ⁵⁴ teə²¹teə²¹ ka³³ na²¹ pæ⁵⁴ rə⁵⁴ka⁵⁴ ɛo²¹ɛa²¹ tʰi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴ fia³³ li³³ ma⁵⁴-ʂu²¹ɛə²¹ yo⁵⁴zə⁵⁴-mu⁵⁴.

Personally, I don't know very much about the schools around our home area because I have been outside most of the time.

[31] Jianfu:

kwe²¹fa⁵⁴ tʂhɛŋ²¹teə²¹ kʰi³³ nda³³ lɛ²¹ tɛ³³. su⁵⁴ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴ dzy²¹-su⁵⁴ o³³ su⁵⁴ kʰi³⁴ sə³³ o³³ tʂo⁵⁴-su⁵⁴ dja³³ lɛ²¹. o²¹ljo²¹ teu⁵⁴je³³fe²¹ sə³³ ʂa²¹kʰo²¹-su⁵⁴ rə⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ ʂə²¹teə⁵⁴ dzo³⁴ sə³³ rə³³ lɛ²¹. a²¹za⁵⁴za⁵⁴-mu⁵⁴ no⁵⁴ væ³³qæ⁵⁴ tʰi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴ na⁵⁴ go⁵⁴ go⁵⁴ dja³³-su⁵⁴ pi²¹teo²³ sə³³n̩i³³ hu⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ tʰi³³ rə⁵⁴ lɛ²¹. tʂhwæ⁵⁴tʂo⁵⁴ ŋu²¹ su²¹ tɛ²¹ o²¹ljo²¹ tʂhwæ⁵⁴ɛiŋ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴ɛwe²¹ ŋu²¹-su²¹ dja³⁴ pa³³. tʂhwæ⁵⁴ɛiŋ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴ɛwe²¹ dja³⁴ ŋu²³ ɛy³³ tɛ³³ o²¹tjo²¹ n̩i²¹mu³³n̩i³³ ŋa³³ tʰa²¹ræ²¹ so²¹ ro³³ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂo⁵⁴ tʰi²¹ga²³ ʂə⁵⁴ʂə⁵⁴ ti²¹-ku²¹ du³³ ku²³ a³³ o²¹tjo²¹ tʂhwæ⁵⁴ɛiŋ⁵⁴ rə⁵⁴ka⁵⁴. tʂhwæ⁵⁴ɛiŋ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴ɛwe²¹ tɛ³³ va⁵⁴ la²¹kʰi³³ na⁵⁴na⁵⁴ o⁵⁴ so²¹ ka³³ teao²¹ɛwe²¹ tʂə²¹nja²¹ kʰi³³ nda⁵⁴ ŋu²¹ ku³³ a³³ n̩i²¹mu³³n̩i³³ ka³³ ŋa³³ o³³ tʰæ²¹ræ²¹ so²¹ tʰa³³ ka³³. o⁵⁴ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂo³³

to²¹ma²¹ndza²¹-su⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ k^hɛŋ⁵⁴ti²¹-ro³³ tæ²¹ʂə²¹ tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ na³³ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂo³³ teao²¹ɛwe²¹ tʂə²¹nja²¹ t^hi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴ ma⁵⁴-sə⁵⁴-ro²¹. no⁵⁴ o³³ lja^o⁵⁴tɛ⁵⁴ mjɛ⁵⁴ a²¹za⁵⁴za⁶⁵-mu⁵⁴.

Guifeng's score is obviously great because schools have come to recruit her in advance. Schools come to recruit only if a score is really high. The schools only start in September, so there is still time. You can send her after taking enough time to compare the schools. Chuanzhong refers to Chuanxing Middle School, right? If it is Chuangxing Middle School, it is near where I studied in Xichang Nationalities Middle School in the direction of Chuanxing. There were only Han Chinese students studying in Chuanxing Middle School, and it was famous for having excellent teaching quality since the time I was studying near that school. It is clear that Chuanzhong is better than Xichang Nationalities Middle School, but I am not sure about the teaching quality difference between the Prefecture Nationalities Middle School and Chuanzhong. You can ask around and slowly figure it out.

[32] Jianfu:

mi²¹tʂo³³ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ tɛ³³ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂo³³ to²¹ma²¹ndza²¹. ʂə²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ su⁵⁴ ʂə²¹ dja³³ so⁵⁴. tʂo⁵⁴ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂo³³-hi²¹-mu⁵⁴ pæ³³-su⁵⁴ dja³⁴ ka³³ taŋ⁵⁴ts^hə²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ k^hi³³-su⁵⁴ lo⁵⁴ tewi²¹tiŋ²¹-mu⁵⁴ ka³³. tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ na⁵⁴ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂo³³ tɛ⁵⁴ ʂao⁵⁴su⁵⁴ mi²¹ts^hu²¹ do⁵⁴bzə²¹-su⁵⁴ ka³³ tʂao²¹ku²¹ ko²¹ko²¹ faŋ³³mje²¹ ti²¹-p^hæ²³p^hæ³³ o³³ mbæ⁵⁴ kæ⁵⁴ t^hi⁵⁴ki⁵⁴. tæ²¹ʂə²¹ teao²¹ɛwe²¹ tʂə²¹nja²¹ tɛ⁵⁴ tʂo⁵⁴mi²¹tʂo³³ p^hæ³³ k^o⁵⁴zə⁵⁴ k^o⁵⁴zə⁵⁴-mu⁵⁴ k^hi³³ kæ⁵⁴-su⁵⁴ k^hŋ⁵⁴ti²¹-mu³³ ʂə²¹mi²¹tʂo³³ to²¹ma²¹ndza²¹ mu²¹.

Regarding nationality middle schools, the prefecture-level nationality middle school is better than the city-level nationality middle school. The city government manages the city-level middle school. The prefecture government manages the prefecture-level middle school, so the prefecture-level middle school is more prestigious. Both schools have mostly minority students, and there may be some opportunities for preferential school fees or scores when they take university entrance exams later. But the teaching quality in the Prefecture Nationalities Middle School is surely better than Xichang Nationalities Middle School.

[33] Jiujiu:

dja³³ŋu²¹ dja³³ŋu²¹. nu³³ ma⁵⁴ jy⁵⁴ sə³³ djɛ³³?

Yes, yes. You are still not sleeping?

[34] Jianfu:

ɛy⁵⁴ɛə²¹ ŋu²¹ ha³³ mbæ⁵⁴-ro²¹. ɛy⁵⁴ɛə²¹ ŋu²¹ ha³³ mbæ⁵⁴-ro²¹.

About to sleep. About to sleep.

[35] Bajin:

pu²¹tsu²¹ ta²¹-su⁵⁴ da²¹ ma²¹ q^ho⁵⁴pa²¹ ma³³-hu⁵⁴ o²¹. tʂ^hə²¹tɛə²¹ k^hi³⁴-ro³³ bjɛ³³ sə³³ni³³ ka³³ rə³³.

We should not only pursue subsidy opportunities. We should send her to schools where the teaching quality is decent.

It was after ten PM, so the conversation was discontinued, but it could have been continued at any later time.

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NON-ENGLISH TERMS

Cheng Zijing 陈紫婧, a person's name	Lizhou 礼州, a place name
Chengdu 成都, place name	Muli 木里, a place name
Chuanxing 川兴, place name	Pixian 郫县, a place name
Chuanzhong 川中, place name	Shi Minzhong 市民中 Xichang Nationalities Middle School
Dashui 大水, place name	Sun Wenquan 孙文泉, a person's name
Guomin 国敏, person name	Wu Siying 吴思颖, a person's name
Li Bajin 李八斤, a person's name	Xiao Jiaying 肖佳英, a person's name
Li Chunxiu 李春秀, a person's name	Xichang 西昌, a place name
Li Guifeng 李贵芬, a person's name	Xichang Nationalities Middle School, Shiminzhong 市民中
Li Jianfu 李建富, Dawa Tenzin, Zla ba bstan 'dzin ལྷ་བ་བསྟན་འཛིན། a person's name	Xingsheng 兴盛, a place name
Li Jibu 李吉布, a person's name	Yang 杨, a person's name
Li Jiujin 李九斤, a person's name	Yang Jiaru 杨佳茹, a person's name
Li Sanjin 李三斤, a person's name	Yangguang 阳光 Yangguang Middle School
Li Xiaolong 李晓龙, a person's name	Yulong 裕隆, a place name
Li Yuchen 李雨晨, a person's name	Zheng Lijia 郑丽佳, a person's name
Liangshan Prefecture Nationalities Middle School, Zhouminzhong 州民中	